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THE ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN MODERN EDUCATION

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Annotation

This paper is about the role of technology in education. It explains how computers, the internet, and mobile phones help students and teachers in their daily learning process. The paper also shows both the good and bad sides of using technology in education. Technology makes studying easier, faster, and more interesting. However, if students use it too much, it can cause problems such as distraction and lack of communication. The purpose of this paper is to show how technology helps education, how students use it every day, and what problems can happen when technology is used too much.

Keywords: technology, education, learning, internet, students

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Introduction

In today's world, technology is everywhere. People use it at work, at home, and at school. We use phones, computers, and the internet every day. Because of technology, our life has become faster and more comfortable. Education has also changed a lot because of technology. In the past, students only used books and notebooks. Now, they can learn by using computers, tablets, and smartphones. Teachers can show pictures, videos, and presentations to make lessons more interesting. According to UNESCO (2023), most schools in the world now use some kind of technology in teaching. Students can study at home using online classes or digital materials. This makes learning more flexible because they can learn anytime and anywhere.

Literature Review

Many researchers have studied the connection between technology and education. Prensky (2001) called modern students "digital natives" because they grow up using technology and understand it better than adults. He said that teachers should use new teaching methods that include technology.

Bates (2015) wrote that technology makes learning more active and helps students remember information better. Students can use online courses, videos, and quizzes to practice what they learn in school.

Cuban (2001) explained that technology is not always good. He said that computers and digital tools do not automatically improve education. Teachers need special training to use them effectively.

According to OECD (2020), students who use technology moderately (not too much and not too little) usually get better grades than those who use it all the time. This means that balance is very important.

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Anderson and Rainie (2021) said that in the future, artificial intelligence and virtual reality will make learning more personalized. For example, computers will help teachers understand what each student needs and give special lessons for them.

Discussion

Technology brings many benefits to education. The first and most important one is easy access to information. Before, students had to go to the library and spend hours looking for books. Now, they can find everything on the internet in just a few seconds. Websites like YouTube, Coursera, and Khan Academy offer free lessons in many subjects such as math, science, and languages.

The second benefit is interactive learning. Students are more interested in lessons when teachers use videos, games, and multimedia. They can see pictures, animations, and real examples. This helps them understand the topic better.

Third, technology allows distance learning. During the COVID-19 pandemic, many schools and universities used online platforms like Zoom and Google Classroom. Students studied from home and sent their homework through the internet. This showed that technology can help continue education even during difficult times.

Technology also helps students with disabilities. For example, special programs can read text aloud for students who cannot see well, or translate words for those who have language difficulties. This makes education more inclusive and fair. However, there are some challenges too. One big problem is distraction. Many students check social media or play games while studying. This makes it difficult for them to focus and remember information.

Parents also need to help. They should control how much time children spend online and encourage them to use technology for studying, not only for fun.

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Picture 1. Empirical Survey Results

Your age:
17 ответов

To understand how students use technology in education, a small survey was done. The participants were young people between 19 and 22 years old.

Picture 2. Empirical Survey Results

what is your status?
17 ответов

What do you use for studying?
17 ответов

According to the results, 58% of the respondents were university students. 60% of them use the internet every day. Most students (41%) use the internet through their mobile phones, while 29% use it on computers.

Picture 3. Empirical Survey Results

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How many hours a day do you use technology for learning?
17 ответов

Does technology make studying easier for you?
16 ответов

In studying, 64% of students said they study for 1 to 3 hours a day. 62% of people want to study with the help of technology because it makes learning more interesting.

Picture 4. Empirical Survey Results

What problems do you have when using technology?
17 ответов

What do you like most about using technology for learning?
17 ответов

Students use technology for different reasons. 41% use it to find information quickly, and 29% use it to understand lessons better.

However, not everything is perfect. 58% of the students said that slow internet is a big problem for them when studying online. These results show that technology is an important part of students' education. Most young people use it every day, but some still face problems like weak internet connection or limited access to devices.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, technology has changed education in many positive ways. It helps students learn faster, find more information, and study from any place. Teachers can use computers and projectors to make lessons more creative and easier to understand.

But technology can also cause problems if used too much. Students can get distracted, addicted, or lazy. Some students may not have access to digital devices, which is unfair.

The best solution is to use technology wisely and in balance. It should help learning, not replace it. Students, teachers, and parents must work together to make sure technology is used for education and personal development.

Technology will continue to grow and become more powerful. If we use it in a smart way, it can make education more modern, fair, and exciting for everyone.

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